

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization BESOO v101

Joseph Nowarski, M.Sc., ME – Energy Conservation Expert

Version 101.01, 25 May 2025

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15511334

all versions DOI:10.5281/zenodo.15511333

Abstract

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization (BESOO) is a system of online internet programs that calculates temperatures, energy and other parameters for various cases and conditions based on input values.

The current version (101) calculates temperatures of the outside wall layers and room air temperature at constant ambient air temperature. This version calculates conduction heat transfer through outside walls only. Solar radiation is not included in the current version.

The online simulation program was successfully validated using the Thermal Time Constant (TTC) method.

This work includes examples of the application of BESOO to determine room air temperature without space heating or air conditioning at various ambient air temperatures and thermal insulation thicknesses.

It may be useful to select optimum building design, especially the location and thickness of insulation, and thermal mass such as a concrete layer.

The online internet program according to this work is available on nowagreen.com/BESO/101 (free, no login required).

Glossary

Ave	Average
COP	Coefficient of Performance of air conditioning
dtau	time period of the integration = integration interval [sec]
kWhTh	kilo-Watt-hour thermal = kWhe * COP – actual heat (+) or cool (-) supplied to the room by air conditioning
kWhe	kilo-Watt-hour electric – electricity consumption by air conditioning [kWh]
Ref	reference
Ta	ambient (outside) air temperature [°C]
Troom	room air temperature [°C]
We	Watt electric – electricity consumption of air conditioning [Wh/hr]
Wth	Watt thermal = We * COP – actual heat (+) or cool (-) supplied to the room by air conditioning

Energy Units

This work is in Metric Units. Energy is expressed in Joule, Ws, or kWh

$$W = J / \text{sec}$$

$$kW = 1,000 J / \text{sec}$$

$$kWh = 1,000 J * 3,600 \text{ sec/hr} = 3,600,000 J$$

Air conditioning electricity power (for cooling or heating) is expressed in [We] (W electric):

$$We = Wth / COP$$

$$kW_e = kWh / COP$$

COP Coefficient of Performance of the air conditioning system

- heat transfer through conduction (heat flow) is expressed in Joule/second

$$1 \text{ J/s} = 1 \text{ W}$$

- change in thermal mass of a layer is expressed in Joules

$$1 \text{ J} = 1 \text{ Ws}$$

$$1 \text{ kWh}_{\text{th}} = 3,600,000 \text{ J}$$

kWh_{th} kWh thermal, in difference to kWh electric [kWh_e]

Building and the Apartment

In this version, the calculations are for the entire apartment and not for individual rooms; the entire apartment is considered one room.

It is assumed that the room temperature in all neighboring apartments is the same as in the tested apartment.

Energy Calculations

In general, energy calculations in this simulation are related to 2 aspects:

- conduction heat transfer through the outside wall layers
- changes in the thermal mass of the outside wall layers

Both cases involve “*temperature difference*” (dt , ΔT , Δt). There is a different meaning of dt (Δt) in the case of conduction heat transfer and the case of change in the thermal mass of the layer.

In the case of conduction, dt (Δt) is the difference between the temperature at the starting point of the heat flow and the endpoint.

In case of a change in the thermal mass of the layer, dt (Δt) is the change of the layer temperature at the same point (in this work at the center of the layer).

To distinguish between conduction and thermal mass, the energy related to the conduction heat flow will be indicated in this work as “Q” and the change in the thermal mass of the layer as “E”.

Radiation heat transfer (like radiation from outside walls to outer space) is not included in this version.

Conduction Heat Transfer Between Layers

For the steady state heat conduction in one dimension, the Fourier equation may be applied [ASHRAE Handbook 1989 – 3.2]:

$$Q = -k * A * (dt/dx)$$

Q	heat flow rate [W]
k	thermal conductivity [W/m,°C]
A	cross-sectional area, normal to flow [m ²]
dx	distance between 2 points of the building element [meter]
dt	temperature difference between the 2 points of dx [°C]
dt/dx	temperature gradient [°C/meter]

Heat flow through many layers caused by temperature difference ($t_{hi} - t_{low}$) may be calculated according to [ASHRAE Handbook 1989 – 3.3]:

Formula 1 - Heat transfer through multi-layer building element

$$Q = U * A * (t_{hi} - t_{low})$$

Q	overall heat transfer through a multi-layer building element (like a few layers of outside wall) [W]
U	overall coefficient of heat transfer [W/m ² ,°C]
A	area normal to the flow (like outside wall total area) [m ²]
($t_{hi} - t_{low}$)	temperature difference between the start point of the heat flow and the endpoint [°C]

Formula 2 - Overall coefficient of heat transfer through multi-layer building element

$$U = \frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^{i_{\max}} r_i}$$

i layer number starting from outside

i_{\max} last layer

r_i thermal resistance of layer i [$\text{m}^2, \text{°C}/\text{W}$]

$$r = Th / \lambda$$

Th thickness of the layer [m]

λ specific thermal conductivity of the layer [$\text{W}/\text{m}, \text{°C}$]

$$k = 1 / r$$

$$k = \lambda / Th$$

k thermal conductivity of the layer [$\text{W}/\text{m}^2, \text{°C}$]

Changes in Thermal Mass of a Layer

The energy changes of the layer will be calculated according to the first Law of Thermodynamics:

$$\frac{de}{d\tau} = q_{in} - q_{out}$$

de energy increase of the layer, per area [J/m^2]

$d\tau$ time period of the integration = integration interval [sec]

q_{in} energy flow into the system [W/m^2]

q_{out} energy flow out from the system [W/m^2]

$$E = e * A$$

$$Q_{in} = q_{in} * A$$

$$Q_{out} = q_{out} * A$$

A area of the construction element [m^2]

$$dE / d\tau = Q_{in} - Q_{out}$$

To simplify the formulas, “dE” will have “E” symbol in this work.

For calculations of the temperature change of the body, specific heat c_p is involved.

The definition of the specific heat is as follows [ASHRAE Handbook 1989 – 3.3]:

$$c_p = \frac{q_{net}}{m * \frac{dt}{d\tau}}$$

c_p specific heat at constant pressure [J/kg,°C]

q_{net} net heat input to the layer, [W/m²]

$$q_{net} = q_{in} - q_{out}$$

As mentioned before, in this work q_{net} has a symbol e [W/m²] or E [W]

$$e = q_{in} - q_{out}$$

q_{in} energy flow into the system [W/m²]

q_{out} energy flow out from the system [W/m²]

m mass of the body (p.e. 1 m² of the concrete layer of the wall) [kg/m²]

dt temperature increase of the body [°C] in period $d\tau$

$d\tau$ integration interval [sec]

$$M = m * A$$

A area of the building element (like wall) [m²]

M mass of the building element [kg]

$$M = A * Th * Rho$$

Th thickness of the layer [m]

Rho density of the material of the layer (like concrete) [kg/m³]

$$MC = M * c_p$$

Formula 3 - Change in layer's temperature

$$dt = (Q_{in} - Q_{out}) * d\tau / MC$$

dt in the above formula is related to the change in the thermal mass of the layer during the time period $d\tau$.

Outside Wall Layers

In this version, the heat flow is from outside the structure to inside. In cases where the heat flow is in the opposite direction, the value of the conductive heat flow [Q] will be negative.

Also according to the TTC formula [4], the outside wall layers numbering starts from outside.

Table 1 - Outside wall layers

Layer #	Layer	Material
Outside air		
0	Outside laminar layer	
1	Outer layer	Stones + Cement Base
2	Outside insulation	PS
3	Central layer	Concrete
4	Inside insulation	PS
5	Inner layer	Gypsum Plaster
r	Inside laminar layer	
Room air		

Table 2 - Conduction heat flow between layers

Q	from	to	from	to
Qo1	Outside air	Center of layer 1	Ta	To1
Qo3	Center of layer 1	Center of layer 3	To1	To3
Qo5	Center of layer 3	Center of layer 5	To3	To5
QoR	Center of layer 5	Room air	To5	Troom

Table 3 - Change in thermal energy of outside wall layers

Layer #	Material	E	Qin	Qout	Temperature
1	Stones + Cement Base	$E_{o1} = Q_{o1} - Q_{o3}$	Q_{o1}	Q_{o3}	T_{o1}
3	Concrete	$E_{o3} = Q_{o3} - Q_{o5}$	Q_{o3}	Q_{o5}	T_{o3}
5	Gypsum Plaster	$E_{o5} = Q_{o5} - Q_{oR}$	Q_{o5}	Q_{oR}	T_{o5}

Change in Thermal Energy of Room Air

Calculations of thermal energy of room air are based on Formula 3:

$$dt = (Q_{in} - Q_{out}) * dtau / MC$$

There are few energy sources in the room. This work includes only the heat transfer from outside walls to the room air– Q_{oR}

$$Q_{in} = Q_{oR}$$

$$Q_{out} = 0$$

Formula 4 - Temperature change in room air

$$dt = Q_{oR} * dtau / M_{Ca}$$

M_{Ca} thermal mass of the air in the room [J/°C]

$$M_{Ca} = M_a * c_{pa}$$

$$M_a = V_a * \rho_a$$

M_{Ca} thermal mass of the air in the room [J/°C]

M_a mass of the air in the room [kg]

V_a volume of the air in the room [m³]

ρ_a density of the air in the room [kg/m³]

c_{pa} specific heat of the air in the room [J/kg,°C]

Air density ρ_a is 1.205 kg/m³ and the specific heat c_{pa} of the room air is 1,007 J/kg,°C [1].

Building Energy Simulation

Formula 5 - UA of outside wall layer

$$UA_{o1} = A_o / (1/H_{out} + Th1/(2*\lambda1))$$

$$UA_{o3} = A_o / [Th1/(2*\lambda1) + Th2/\lambda2 + Th3/(2*\lambda3)]$$

$$UA_{o5} = A_o / [Th3/(2*\lambda3) + Th4/\lambda4 + Th5/(2*\lambda5)]$$

$$UA_{oR} = A_o / [Th5/(2*\lambda5) + 1/H_{in}]$$

UA_o	thermal conductivity of outside wall layers included in UA calculations [W/°C]
A_o	area of outside wall [m ²]
H_{out}	conductivity of the outside laminar layer [W/m ² ,°C]
i	layer number
Th_i	thickness of layer i [meter]
λ_i	specific conductivity of the material of layer i [W/m,°C]
H_{in}	conductivity of inside laminar layer [W/m ² ,°C]

It is assumed in this work that the average layer temperature is in the center of the layer, therefore, each UA applies only half of the first and the last layer.

Formula 6 - Conduction heat transfer through outside wall layers (Q), W/°C

Conduction heat transfer through outside wall layers is based on Formula 1:

$$Q = U * A * (t_{hi} - t_{low})$$

$$Q_{o1} = UA_{o1} * (T_a - T_{o1})$$

$$Q_{o3} = UA_{o3} * (T_{o1} - T_{o3})$$

$$Q_{o5} = UA_{o5} * (T_{o3} - T_{o5})$$

$$Q_{oR} = UA_{oR} * (T_{o5} - T_{room})$$

Formula 7 - Simulation of temperature

In the programming language, the simulation of the temperature has the following form:

$$T_{new} = T_{last} + dt$$

T_{new} new temperature of the body [°C]
 T_{last} last temperature of the body [°C]
 dt temperature increase of the body [°C] in period dt

Example of Well-Insulated Apartment

Table 4 - Well-insulated apartment outside wall data

Layer #	Layer	Material	Thickness	Density	Mass	Specific Heat	Specific Heat	MC	Thermal Conductivity	Thermal Resistance	Ref
Units			M	kg/m3	kg/m2	Wh/kg,°C	J/kg,°C	J/°C,m2	W/m,°C	m2,°C/W	
			Th	Rho	M	cp	cp	MC	λ	r	
Outside air											
0	Outside laminar layer									0.040	[6]
1	Outer layer	Stones + Cement Base	0.100	2,120	212	0.24	860	182,320	1.442	0.069	[2]
2	Outside insulation	PS	0.040	30	1.2	0.40	1,440	1,728	0.032	1.250	[2]
3	Central layer	Concrete	0.200	2,400	480	0.27	970	465,600	2.100	0.095	[6]
4	Inside insulation	PS	0.000	30	0	0.40	1,440	0	0.032	0.000	[2]
5	Inner layer	Gypsum Plaster	0.015	1,200	18	0.30	1,080	19,440	0.350	0.043	[6]
6	Inside laminar layer									0.145	[6]
Room air											
Total			0.355		711		941	669,088		1.642	

The following chart is for a well-insulated apartment for a constant ambient air temperature of 10°C. The initial air temperature in the room is 20°C.

Chart 1 - Room air temperature °C at the end of the day, $T_a=10^\circ\text{C}$

Validation of the Simulation Program

The validation is done using Thermal Time Constant - TTC. Publications [3] [4] include a formula for the TTC calculation. Application of this formula for the above example results in $TTC = 194.0725$ hours, which means that in 194 hours the temperature difference will decrease by 63.2%. More details regarding the TTC may be found in publications [3] [4].

In the above example of the BESOO simulation, the ambient air temperature was set to constant 10°C, while the initial room air temperature was 20°C.

Considering the temperature difference of 10°C (20°C inside the room, 10°C outside), after 194 hours the room temperature should drop to 13.6788°C.

The simulation with $d\tau=1.0$ sec shows this room temperature after 196.3333 hours. At the TTC time, the simulation room air temperature was 13.7209°C, 0.04°C above the TTC temperature.

Running the simulation with $d\tau=0.5$ seconds did not change the results.

Table 5 - Differences between the TTC method [4] and the simulation

	TTC	Simulation	
Outside temperature Ta,		10	°C
Room air initial temperature, Troom		20	°C
Initial Δt		10	°C
Δt change after 1 TTC	63.2121%		%
Δt change after 1 TTC	6.3212		°C
Room temperature after 1 TTC	13.6788		°C
TTC	194.0725		hr
TTC days	8		days
+ hours:minutes	2:04		hr
Simulation room air temperature at TTC time		13.7209	°C
Temperature difference at TTC time		0.0421	°C
Temperature difference at TTC time		0.3081%	
Simulation time at TTC temperature		196.3333	hr
Time difference of 1 TTC temperature		2.2608	hr
Time difference of 1 TTC temperature		1.1649%	
Average difference between TTC and simulation		0.7365%	

Considering very small differences from the TTC method, the simulation was successfully validated.

BESOO Simulation Examples – Ambient Temperature

Table 6 - Input data for all examples - winter

Initial room air temperature	20	°C
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.100	m
outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.040	m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.200	m
inner insulation layer (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.000	m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	0.015	m
TTC	194.073	hr

Table 7 - Winter simulation results

Fix Ta, °C	Troom after 1 day, °C	Troom after 5 days, °C	Troom after 10 days, °C
-40	+14.17	-7.13	-22.40
-30	+15.14	-2.61	-15.33
-20	+16.11	+1.91	-8.26
-10	+17.08	+6.43	-1.20
0	+18.06	+10.96	+5.87
+10	+19.03	+15.48	+12.93

Table 8 - Input data for all examples - summer

Initial room air temperature	25	°C
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.100	m
outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.040	m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.200	m
inner insulation layer (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.000	m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	0.015	m
TTC	194.073	hr

Table 9 - Summer simulation results

Fix Ta, °C	Troom after 1 day, °C	Troom after 5 days, °C	Troom after 10 days, °C
+30	+25.49	+27.26	+28.53
+35	+25.97	+29.52	+32.07
+40	+26.46	+31.78	+35.60
+45	+26.94	+34.04	+39.13
+50	+27.43	+36.30	+42.67

BESOO Simulation Examples – Location of Insulation Layer

Table 10 - Input data for all cases

Fix Ta	0	°C
Initial room air temperature	20	°C
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.100	m
insulation layer (2) or (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.040	m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.200	m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	0.015	m

Table 11 - Insulation location

insulation 4 cm PS	TTC, hr	Troom after 1 day, °C	Troom after 5 days, °C	Troom after 10 days, °C
outer insulation layer (2)	194.07	+18.06	+10.96	+5.87
inner insulation layer (4)	32.45	+11.69	+0.23	+0.00
no insulation	25.3	+8.03	+0.13	+0.00

Chart 2 - Insulation location – room air temperature in 10 days, °C

BESOO Simulation Examples – Insulation Thickness

Table 12 - Input data for all examples

Fix Ta	0	°C
Initial room air temperature	20	°C
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.100	m
outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.040	m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.200	m
inner insulation layer (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.000	m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	0.015	m

Table 13 - Insulation thickness

outer insulation - layer 2	TTC, hr	Troom after 1 day, °C	Troom after 5 days, °C	Troom after 10 days, °C
2 cm	109.61	+16.62	+6.78	+2.21
3 cm	151.82	+17.53	+9.23	+4.14
4 cm	194.07	+18.06	+10.96	+5.87

Chart 3 - Insulation thickness – room air temperature in 10 days, °C

Website

Chart 4 - [BESOO online simulation input page \[7\]](https://nowagreen.com/BESOO/101/)

Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization - BESOO page 101, v101.01
Change of room air temperature with time
Fix ambient air temperature, no heat or AC, outside walls only

The outer insulation (layer 2) and the inner insulation (layer 4) is Polystyrene Foam (PS) - 0.0320 W/m.°C thermal conductivity.
If other thermal insulation is applied, the insulation thickness may be corrected to the PS equivalent. For example, insulation with 10% higher conductivity should be submitted to the following input table with 10% lower thickness.

fix ambient air temperature	10 °C
initial room air temperature	20 °C
room height	2.65 m
outside wall part 1 length	10 m
outside wall part 2 length	10 m
outer layer (1) stone and cement thickness	0.100 m
outer insulation layer (2) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0.040 m
central layer (3) concrete thickness	0.200 m
inner insulation layer (4) Polystyrene Foam thickness	0 m
inner plaster layer (5) gypsum plaster thickness	0.015 m

Submit (also with: Alt s)

This simulation program is based on research "Building Energy Simulation and Optimization - BESOO" by Joseph Nowarski and G. L. Esterson, presented at First Joint Conference of International Simulation Societies, 22-25 August 1994, ETH Zurich, Switzerland.

Chart 5 - [BESOO online simulation results page \[7\]](https://nowagreen.com/BESOO/101/101.php)

simulation completed, simulation time: 0 sec
simulation results:

24/05/2025 11:29:42 GMT			
nowagreen.com BESOO page 101, v101.01, no Heat/AC, Fix Ta, Fix Initial Troom, Outside Wall only			
page	no Heat/AC	101	
URL	https://nowagreen.com/BESOO/101		
Version	v	101.01	
Integration Interval	dtau	1	sec
Thermal Time Constant	TTC	194	hours
Fix Ambient Temperature	Ta	10	°C
Initial Room Air Temperature	TroomStart	20	°C
Room Air Temperature after 10 days	Troom	12.933923206345	°C

download CSV file with hours temperatures (°C) every 10 minutes

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cite this page:
Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization - BESOO v101.01 - Joseph Nowarski
<https://nowagreen.com/BESOO/101>
(c) nowarski@gmail.com

References

1. Efficient Simulation of Building Energy Systems Using Personal Computers - Joseph Nowarski, G. L. Esterson, CISS: First Joint Conference of International Simulation Societies Proceedings, August 22-25, 1994 ETH Zurich, Switzerland, ISBN 1-56555-031-5
2. The solution for improving the Thermal Time Constant (TTC) of buildings - Dr. Eng. David Sragovich, Israeli Ministry of National Infrastructures, December 2000
3. Energy and Thermal Time Constant in Buildings – Joseph Nowarski
<https://www.amazon.com/dp/B01F18XGQK>
4. Thermal Time Constant – TTC, v2.1.1 - Joseph Nowarski,
DOI:10.5281/zenodo.6530723
5. The Government Databases / Meteorological Service
<https://ims.data.gov.il/ims/7>
6. Thermal Insulation of Buildings: Residential Buildings – Israeli Standard 1045.1 - 1997
7. Online Building Energy Simulation and Optimization - BESOO page 101, v101.01
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Fix ambient air temperature, no heat or AC, outside walls only
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